

INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL SUPPORT FOR THE ACTIVITIES OF THE CRIMINAL INVESTIGATION SERVICE UNITS OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14575273>

Abstract: The article examines the issues of implementing analytical work as one of the main functions of the innovative development of information and analytical support for the activities of the criminal investigation service units of the internal affairs bodies. Information and analytical work is presented as a tool that allows for high-quality processing of information to make the most effective management decision on conducting operational-search activities in disclosure and investigation.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, criminal investigation service, information and analytical support, operational-search activities, crime detection, operational-search activities.

As part of the large-scale reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to ensuring a peaceful and tranquil life for the population, as well as fostering a culture of law-abidingness and public safety in our society.

At the same time, various increasing threats and conflicts in the world, risks to peace and tranquility of the country, natural and man-made disasters impose on responsible state structures the task of further improving their activities based on the priority idea of "All efforts for human dignity." The measures taken have made it possible to enhance the role of internal affairs bodies, transforming them into a socially oriented professional structure where each employee unconditionally fulfills their service duty - "Serving the interests of the people."

The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-60 of January 28, 2022, "On the Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026," sets the goal of "ensuring the preparation, publication, and widespread dissemination of information and analytical reviews dedicated to the results of the implementation of the Development Strategy and the State Program in foreign languages" [1].

Therefore, the Ministry of Internal Affairs has developed a number of measures to effectively organize information and analytical activities for the innovative development of information and analytical support for operational-search service units in internal affairs bodies. Our country has implemented comprehensive measures aimed at improving the system of internal affairs bodies, strengthening their lower levels, bringing them closer to the population, clearly defining the tasks and functions of structures at all levels, and rationally distributing forces and resources, taking into account modern threats. [2]

These measures are an important tool for transforming internal affairs bodies into a truly people-oriented system, in which it is crucial to constantly improve their activities in the areas of management, information analysis, forecasting, and control. This is because the innovative development of information and analytical support for operational-search service units is of great importance. Therefore, existing problems in the field of maintaining public

order, crime prevention, and combating crime will be studied and analyzed to bring them to a qualitatively new level. This allows for the implementation of an effective mechanism for in-depth analysis, identification, and elimination of the causes and conditions for the commission of crimes.[3]

The effective organization and management of the innovative development of information and analytical support for the activities of operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies is a complex process, the complexity of which depends on: firstly, regular study and accurate assessment of the operational situation in the region; secondly, timely and effective planning of this activity; thirdly, regular change of tactical methods depending on the operational situation in carrying out activities; fourthly, timely and effective use of scientific and technical innovations; fifthly, widespread introduction of best practices in the

Effective activity of management entities of internal affairs bodies in maintaining public order and combating crime depends, firstly, on the proper organization of information and analytical support for the activities of operational-search service units; secondly, on the clear definition of tasks related to analytical activities; thirdly, on ensuring effective cooperation between other units and the public in organizing information and analytical activities of internal affairs bodies and collecting information.

Effective organization of activities for the innovative development of information and analytical support for operational-search service units includes collecting and analyzing information, making decisions based on it, forecasting crime and planning the fight against it, and correctly evaluating the achieved results, organizing and monitoring the implementation of decisions.

The effective organization of innovative development of information and analytical support for the activities of operational-search service units depends, first and foremost, on the completeness, reliability, and quality of the information received. Therefore, they are required to identify, collect, and comprehensively analyze all information about the objects that should be prioritized for preventive measures.

The peculiarities and significance of the innovative development of information and analytical support for the activities of the operational-search service units of the internal affairs bodies are manifested in adapting to the operational situation and introducing them to the main tasks and methods of crime prevention, in eliminating the influence of false information that hinders the prevention of crimes, in managing the activities of various bodies, institutions, public organizations, and self-government bodies of citizens in crime prevention.

In accordance with the requirements of current regulatory legal acts, the collection, systematization, analysis of data and identification of data sources in the innovative development of information and analytical support for the activities of units of the operational-search service in the internal affairs bodies are carried out in the following order:

establishing the procedure for compiling and providing a list of information and analytical data;

establishing contacts with other relevant state bodies and self-government bodies of citizens and public organizations for the purpose of collecting information;

assessment of the significance, completeness and reliability of the incoming information;

systematization of data by content, direction, and relevance, as well as the formation of a database.

Based on these sources of information, within the framework of the information and analytical activities of the internal affairs bodies, the forces and means of the internal affairs bodies are coordinated and distributed, taking into account the operational and criminogenic situation arising in the service area.

In internal affairs bodies, comprehensive analysis is used to influence the operational-service activities and the resulting criminogenic situation, reduce crime development, and develop measures to identify and eliminate shortcomings and problems in operational-service activities. Comprehensive analysis in internal affairs bodies aims to analyze and evaluate the operational situation in the service area, the results of operational-service activities, the effective use of forces and resources, and influencing external factors. It is carried out to increase the effectiveness of work to stabilize the criminogenic situation.

In the process of managing the information and analytical activities of internal affairs bodies, such forms of comprehensive analysis as current, periodic, prospective, extraordinary, problematic, and comparative are used. [4]

Operational-search activities (OSA) as a distinct type of legal activity are carried out by specially authorized state bodies, their operational units, and officials at all stages of our country's development solely for the purpose of combating crime. This activity is subordinate to the interests of successfully addressing crime-fighting challenges, and its main goal is to effectively protect the rights and interests of citizens, public organizations, and the state as safeguarded by law through conducting operational-search measures. It would be incorrect to view the current activities of operational units carrying out OSA in organizing the fight against crime merely as a set of specific measures to prevent and expose criminal manifestations. In modern society, the fight against crime is a complex set of socio-economic, legal, organizational, special, and other measures implemented by all state bodies and public organizations. These include special measures carried out with the help of operational-search forces, means, and methods. These special measures are closely linked to other actions carried out by state bodies and public organizations and determine the direction of operational-search activities.

In our opinion, planning and organizing any activity based on analysis will be effective. Similarly, a positive outcome can be achieved by planning the detection of committed crimes based on assumptions, taking into account the method, time, place, and other mechanisms of their commission.

In recent years, the emergence of new types, forms, and manifestations of crime worldwide, the changing methods of committing crimes, particularly crimes committed in connection with social networks, the internet, and cybercrime, have placed additional tasks on structures engaged in organizing operational-search activities.

Specifically, the task has been set to improve the information and analytical support of the activities of operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies in the following areas.

In particular, increasing the effectiveness of measures to combat organized crime, terrorism and extremism, and illegal trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. This includes introducing fundamentally new mechanisms to combat crimes in the field of information technology and internet use; providing hardware and software

support for the activities of operational units, and widely implementing modern information technologies.

Considering that the majority of crimes committed in recent years involve information technology, it is necessary to utilize the capabilities of specialists in solving this type of crime and establish effective cooperation with them.

Strengthening daily monitoring and departmental control of heads of operational-search units to increase the effectiveness of measures aimed at uncovering crimes and operational-search activities.

Information and analytical support for the activities of operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies is carried out based on the results of current analysis of daily, weekly, and monthly outcomes. It is aimed at meeting the daily needs of operational management and supporting the daily activities of internal affairs personnel. Based on this analysis, measures are taken to address specific offenses and crimes, necessary adjustments are made for the deployment of forces and resources, and other management actions are implemented.

It aims to identify trends in offenses and crimes, analyze the operational and service activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as the causes of shortcomings and problems. Based on this analysis, proposals are prepared to improve the effectiveness of operational and service activities in the upcoming period, and practical and organizational action plans are developed.

In long-term analysis, the information and analytical support for operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies is examined over a period exceeding one year to promote innovative development. It focuses on identifying causes of crimes specific to the service area and analyzing systemic issues in crime prevention and law enforcement. Based on this analysis, comprehensive and targeted programs are developed to enhance the effectiveness of operational and service activities.

The innovative development of information and analytical support for operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies is determined through the following methods:

Expert evaluation - allows for the identification of changes in crime in a specific area or by type through surveys among industry experts;

Modeling - enables the construction of mathematical models and development of conclusions about expected changes in crime based on studying relationships between criminogenic factors;

Extrapolation - permits the analysis of previously established criminogenic situations under identical conditions, studying the causes and circumstances of their occurrence, and consequently identifying changes in the existing criminogenic situation [5].

It is conducted to identify the causes of problems in the operational and service activities of two or more internal affairs bodies operating under similar conditions.

As a result of comprehensive analysis of information and analytical activities in the innovative development of information and analytical support for operational-search service units of internal affairs bodies, reference documents, notifications, and analytical reports are prepared.

These documents should include a brief description of the criminogenic situation, results of operational-service activities, shortcomings and problems, their root causes, outcomes of operational-search activities in specific areas, positive achievements and contributing factors,

exemplary internal affairs units based on performance results, deficiencies in operational-service activities, as well as information about internal affairs bodies with poor service performance, causes of errors and responsible officials, proposals and recommendations for addressing shortcomings, and draft management decisions for their implementation.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [Electronic source]. - URL: <http://www.lex.uz>
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-344 dated December 25, 2012 "On Operational-Search Activities." (Article 26) Source: <https://lex.uz/docs/2107763>.
3. Khamdamov A.A., Saitbaev T.R., Gordeev S.N., Rashidkhodjaev R.T. Commentary on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Operational-Search Activities." T-2015. pp. 3-4.
4. Fundamentals of management and information-analytical activities in internal affairs bodies: Textbook / I. Ismailov, D.S. Mukhamadaliev, E.U. Azizov; responsible editor B. Matlyubov. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019 - 432 p.
5. Matchanov A.A. Information and reference support for the detection and investigation of crimes. Monograph. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2001. - 126 p.